

Copper(III) as an Oxidative Titrant for Alanine, 2-aminobutyric Acid and Arginine monohydrochloride

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PREPARATION, standardisation and applications of tellurato cuprate(III) have been described in earlier publications¹⁻³. The present communication describes the microdetermination of alanine, 2-aminobutyric acid and arginine monohydrochloride using Cu(III).

butyric acid and arginine monohydrochloride were of B.D.H. biochemical grade.

Procedure : An aliquot of the aqueous solution containing 1.0-3.5 μ moles of amino acid was added to an excess of Cu(III) reagent ($1.56 \times 10^{-4} \mu$ moles). The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate for 15 minutes, cooled and the unconsumed Cu(III) determined as described earlier¹. Total volume of solution mixture was kept 20 ml. Blank experiments were also conducted under identical conditions. The results are given in Table 1.

References

1. S. CHANDRA and K. L. YADAVA, *Talanta*, 1968, 15, 349.
2. P. K. JAISWAL and S. CHANDRA, *Chimie Anal.*, 1969, 51, 493.
3. P. K. JAISWAL, *Microchem. J.*, 1970, 15, 434.

TABLE I—OXIDATION OF ALANINE, 2-AMINO BUTYRIC ACID AND ARGININE MONOHYDROCHLORIDE USING TELLURATO COPPER (III) REAGENT

Amino Acid	Amount of amino acid taken μ mole.	Copper (III) consumed equiv./mole of amino acid*			Error %
		a	b	c	
Alanine	2.94	2.42	5.56	19.90	-0.5
2-Aminobutyric acid	2.52	1.64	6.70	25.96	-0.15
Arginine monohydrochloride	1.27	2.52	9.00	55.82	-0.32

* Mean of six results.

- (a) Determination of Cu(III) immediately after adding the amino acid solution.
- (b) Determination of Cu(III) after allowing the solution mixture to stand for 15 minutes at room temperature.
- (c) Determination of Cu(III) after refluxing and cooling the reaction mixture for 15 minutes.

It has been found that alanine, 2-aminobutyric acid and arginine monohydrochloride required 20,26 and 56 equivalents of the oxidant respectively for their complete oxidation. The results are reproducible within $\pm 0.5\%$. Tellurate does not interfere as oxidant, since Cu(III) being a stronger oxidant, reoxidises any tellurite that may be formed in the reaction mixture. It was also observed that refluxing and cooling of the reaction mixture is essential to complete the oxidation, as determination of Cu(III) immediately after mixing or after allowing to stand for 15 minutes at room temperature gave erroneous results indicating incomplete oxidation.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Telluratocuprate(III) reagent was prepared and standardised as described earlier¹. Alanine, 2-amino-

Binary and Ternary Chelates of Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III) with Ethylenediamine tetraacetic Acid as Primary Ligand and Substituted Salicylic Acids as Secondary Ligands

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ETHYLENEDIAMINETETRAACETIC acid (edta) behaves as a polydentate ligand and forms strong complexes with metal ions in solution at low pH values¹⁻⁴, which remain stable at higher pH as well. Thus, edta has widely been used as one of the constituents in the study of a number of ternary complexing systems.

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